

Reaction with *N*-Bromosuccinic Acid: Synthesis of 7,8-Dimethoxyisocoumarin**

Pratul Kumar Banerjee and D. N. Chaudhury

Adopting the same sequence of reactions using dihydroisocoumarins, as reported earlier¹, 3,4-dihydro-7,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin (I: R=H)² was treated with NBS in presence of benzoyl peroxide to furnish 4-bromo-3,4-dihydro-7,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin (I: R = Br) in 95% yield. The bromo compound on prolonged reflux with triethylamine afforded 7,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin (II), m.p. 149-50°, in 90% yield.

Ribbens *et al.*³ reported the preparation of the same isocoumarin (II) by an altogether different method. Opianic acid was condensed with 2-phenyloxazolin-5-one and the resulting 4-(2-carboxy-3,4-dimethoxybenzylidene)-2-phenyloxazolin-5-one was treated successively with alkali and acid to provide a mixture of benzoic acid and 7,8 dimethoxyisocoumarin-3-carboxylic acid. The latter on decarboxylation yielded 7,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin (II), m.p. 105.5-107°.

We are unable to account for the wide divergence in the m.p. of our product with that recorded by Ribbens *et al.*³. Their experiment could not be repeated due to nonavailability of opianic acid and their product purporting to be (II) could not be compared with our material. Nevertheless, it may be pointed out that in their method of preparation, the penultimate step furnished a mixture of two acids; the lower m.p. may be attributed to their incomplete separation.

*4-Bromo-3,4-dihydro-7,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin (I: R=Br).—A mixture of 3,4-dihydro-7,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin² (100 mg.), NBS (94 mg.), and benzoyl peroxide (1 mg.) in pure dry CCl₄ (5ml) was refluxed for 3 hr. on a water bath, the reaction flask being kept

**This note is to be considered as Part XII of the series "Dihydroisocoumarin".

1. Srivastava and Chaudhury, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 4347; this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 865; Mukhopadhyaya and Chaudhury, *ibid.*, 1963, 40, 433.

2. Banerjee and Chaudhury, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 4344.

3. *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1960, 79, 78.

*All m.p.s uncorrected. Microanalyses by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford, England.

close to an illuminated 60-watt lamp. The reaction mixture was cooled and filtered from succinimide, the filtrate was washed thoroughly with water, and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent left a thick paste of needles which were crystallised several times from ethyl acetate (ice chest) to yield the pure *dihydroisocoumarin* (I: R=Br) (130 mg., 95%) as colorless rosettes of needles, m.p. 142°. (Found: C, 45.5; H, 3.7; Br, 27.1. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{Br}$ requires C, 45.9; H, 3.8; Br, 27.5%).

*7,8-Dimethoxyisocoumarin (II).—The above bromo compound (100 mg.) in triethylamine (10 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 48 hr. The excess triethylamine was removed by evaporation and the solid residue washed with HCl (dil.) and water, collected, and dried in an exiccator. Sublimation *in vacuo* afforded a white crystalline solid, m.p. 146-49°. Recrystallisation from ethyl acetate-petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) furnished the pure *isocoumarin* (II) as colorless, elongated needles (89 mg., 90%), m.p. 149-50° (lit.³ m.p. 105.5-107°). (Found: C, 64.0; H, 4.4. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 64.1; H, 4.8%).

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
L. S. COLLEGE,
BIHAR UNIVERSITY,
MUZAFFARPUR.

Received November 6, 1963.